

Psychological Problems Using Offensive Therapy and Applied Psychotherapy Methods

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or a mental health doctor (it is more recommended to be a specialist). There are many methods used in the treatment of psychological disorders that occur in one or more of the individuals at the same time. Generally, when you talk to a specialist mental health doctor, the method that that mental health doctor will recommend and apply to you goes along with psychotherapy methods that are changed and decided in accordance with your illness or diseases, in addition to drug treatment. In this way, the disease will be overcome more easily. The techniques to be applied in psychotherapy can also be changed and the method to be applied can be decided depending on how much time has passed since the onset of the individual's illness. Especially if the degree of mental illness in the individual has advanced, emergency intervention may be required. For this reason, offensive therapy can be applied in these and similar situations. At the same time, if the individual's mental health doctor starts quickly in case of illness, then with the therapy method that he will apply more slowly but still correctly, he can help the individual overcome his psychological illness more easily. In this article, offensive therapy method and other psychotherapy methods will be examined in depth and as a result, it will be tried to give you as much information as possible.

1- What is Offensive Therapy? What Does It Work?

Offensive therapy, which is applied in compressed intense sessions as the main purpose and is expected to be applied to all kinds of other emergency patients, is called a psychotherapy method applied to sick individuals who want to cover serious distances in a short time, if mental health doctors recommend it. While it is seen as a shortcut way to reach the result in some problems, it can mean making a solid start in some problems. These varying situations consist of three stages: attack therapy, story-taking-psycho-education-behavior change, which is carried out between 30-40 sessions (adjusted to be completed within 15-20 days) according to the problem and personality structure of the individual. In the story-taking stage, which is also considered as the first stage, on the one hand, information about the past life of the client and especially the events that traumatized the person are analyzed in detail by obtaining detailed and necessary information, and on the other hand, the client's review of his own life and at the same time the period for reviewing this life are evaluated. It is aimed to create a therapeutic alliance with the sharing made throughout. In the psychoeducation part, the main aim is to have information about the sources of the problems that the individual has experienced, to make sense of it and to create insight. At the same time, going down to the cause of some events will

CURRENT SCIENCE

cause individuals to think more objectively, so they can make more accurate assessments. In the last stage of offensive therapy, the main target point is to develop all relevant and relevant skills related to the change and control of the emotions, thoughts and behaviors that are the subject of the complaint, and this is targeted by the mental health doctor. After the attack therapy is over, the mental health doctor applies a psychotherapy process with a reduced intensity depending on the condition of the client, to support all the mood development caused by the rapid onset effect, as well as to support the mood change and prevent psychological regression. This situation varies depending about both the mental health doctor and the patient who has consulted this mental health doctor. Offensive therapy generally works for most patients in a short time, causing them to make a very good progress. However, in some patients, this is sometimes not the case because it varies according to the circumstances, and as a result, the mental health doctor changes the psychotherapy method according to the patient's condition, increases the tempo when necessary, or slows the tempo when necessary. In this way, in a short time, thanks to offensive therapy, it is aimed and necessary to get a detailed story of the patient's emotion and thought state, to understand the reasons or causality of the emotions that are effective in this story, to take a distance in the process of change and transformation. The offensive therapy process is generally very difficult for clients who are very disturbed by their problems and want to go a long way quickly (within approximately 2 to maximum 3 weeks), and clients whose disease is quite advanced and need immediate intervention, because they come from outside the province or abroad. It is a psychotherapy method recommended for clients with limited time. It is highly beneficial in serious problems such as obsessive-compulsive disorder, panic disorder, anxiety disorders, depression, fears of abandonment, sexual dysfunctions, and many other serious psychological diseases, and in almost every client who is given offensive therapy, which of course may vary according to the relevant mental health doctor, is observed.

2- Why Offensive Therapy?

With a problem or symptom, they experience, clients apply to clinics that are working on mental health disorders or to the relevant departments of hospitals that are also working on mental health. The basic motivations of individuals in this regard; It is to get rid of this symptom, symptom (panic attack, OCD, depression, etc.) or negative emotions (worthlessness, inadequacy, anger, etc.) that poison their lives as quickly as possible and again as soon as

CURRENT SCIENCE

possible. During this process, most of the time, individuals may want to see rapid changes in their lives and leave their psychotherapy studies with a tangible gain. However, psychotherapy studies; they appear as types of work that can provide changes in the long run. The reason for this is that the mental health doctor and therapist must know the patient very well to analyze the person very well, and at the same time, in addition to this, the individual must determine the source of the problem in the most accurate way. This situation: it can be thought of as making various measurements of all different types, such as MRI, blood test, and many more, for the person who applies to the hospital with a physiological problem (headache, heartache, earache, sore throat, bone pain, joint pain, etc.). Sometimes a headache can be just a headache. However, in some cases, it can be a signal of a very important disease in the body at other times, this condition called a minor headache. Intervening without detecting it does not solve the problem, and in addition, it does not solve it, but also offers the opportunity to cause bigger problems in the future.

Due to reasons like these, the mental health professional, the therapist, must listen to the story of the person applying for therapy with a professional point of view, without making subjective comments and impartially. Listening to the client in this way yields very important information about the origin of the symptom. This information about the client's life also helps the mental health doctor to create a roadmap in his mind about where and how to intervene in the client's mental world. When clients do not see the rapid change they expect, they desperately want to terminate therapy, terminate it, or force themselves to continue desperately. As a matter of fact, the rate of individuals who consulted mental health doctors in Turkey, especially in our country, to drop out of therapy in the first 3 months is around 85%. Thus, the therapy process, which they started with a very difficult decision and very confident in themselves, ends in failure. What they learned after this situation in which they were in despair; that the problems they experience are so bad that they do not go away and that they do not let go of them throughout their lives. Individuals cling tightly to this negative thought that they can say to themselves when they are in trouble and justify their despair. And then, although they do not continue, they find the fault with the mental health doctor they consulted and start to take some actions such as easing their conscience. Individuals "I also went to therapy, but nothing changed." Now, as a last resort, they start looking for unreal remedies like fortune-tellers, amulet writers and magician teachers that will only satisfy them in the moment. If the person does not believe in such things depending on the culture he grew up in or the culture around him, the environment or education level; They turn to different areas that they believe will offer solutions such as

CURRENT SCIENCE

reiki, subconscious cleansing, meditation, which never offer permanent solutions only in the treatment of mental problems But give hope to individuals for a short time by satisfying them now.

With offensive therapy, it is ensured that the person is prevented from having such a negative experience. Because offensive therapy is a therapy method that achieves great results in a very short time, and it contributes to individuals gaining a more hopeful perspective on therapy and increasing their sense of trust towards the mental health doctor and therapist they have consulted. Offensive therapy consists of two phases. In the first 15 sessions of this two-stage offensive therapy, in addition to various information about almost all family members who have had a primary impact on the client's life, memories about these people are taken and attention is paid to these points, especially if there are traumatic situations. At the same time, it can be determined how the individual responds to his traumas by paying attention to the attitude of the person while telling the memories and the points he takes to defend himself. In addition, all the experiences, relationships, traumas, sorrows, joys, losses, turning points, goals, successes, failures, feelings, and things that the client has avoided feeling are listened to from the moment he was born to the present. After that, after 15 sessions, the second stage is started quite quickly. In the remaining 15 sessions, psychological information or psychologically empowering psychotherapy methods are applied to the client, and the procedures and practices determined by targeting the person to have a better psychology are carried out. Here, the client is informed about the mental structure of the individual, the stages of spiritual development, the formation processes of the individual's personality, the ways of self-protection of the mind.

With psycho-information, especially for the person who does not know what he is experiencing most of the time or where or what the root of the problem stems from, what he is experiencing and why becomes meaningful. The meaning of the unknown, feelings, thoughts, past traumas, future fears, and concerns often relieves the person, and after this relief, it aims to reduce or eliminate the symptoms or negative emotions in the individual to a large extent, thereby achieving a positive result.

In addition, at the beginning of the treatment, the client; The individual who has consulted that mental health doctor is asked by the mental health doctor to bring all kinds of old photographs and diaries, if any, found at home. In this process, it is very important to write down the dreams that he has seen and bring them to the session, and it is requested to do this. The information obtained here also provides important contributions to the psychological analysis of the client.

CURRENT SCIENCE

Of course, the same therapy method is not used for every mental disorder and every psychological disease, it cannot be used, and its use is not recommended. Every conscious mental health doctor pays attention to this issue and determines the psychotherapy method psychologically depending on the patient's condition and illness, rather than taking it easy. In psychological diseases, there are many psychotherapy methods that vary according to each patient, each client's situation, and are decided according to the recommendations of the consulted mental health doctor.

3- Psychoanalytic Therapy

Psychoanalytic therapy emerges as a psychotherapy technique that emerged from Sigmund Freud's psychoanalysis in the 19th century and adopted the basic principles of psychoanalysis. Psychoanalytic therapy is often done with the help of face-to-face meetings, once or twice a week. The main aim of psychoanalytic therapy is to gain insight by bringing the unconscious material to the level of consciousness that the individual can easily be aware of, to find the balance in the inner world of the person, to ensure that he is in a strong and harmonious spirituality, and to be at a point as far away from unwanted repetitive patterns as possible. With psychoanalytic therapy, the person's attaining an integrated self, increasing the functionality of the individual and encouraging creative expression can be done on this psychotherapy technique. Although psychoanalytic psychotherapy is a theory of personality, it is also used as a method of psychotherapy and as a scientific research and scientific study tool. Sigmund Freud, who works on personality structure and personality organization in therapy, not only found it, but also helped a lot. It uses psychoanalytic theories when considered as the working, framework, and formulation of this psychotherapy process. As there is a relationship between theory and technique, an important relationship is also established between ethics and technique. Ethics becomes a part of technique in psychoanalysis and emerges as a fundamental requirement of psychoanalytic practice.

The basic philosophy in psychoanalytic psychotherapy: Individuals can be under the influence of sexual and aggressive impulses, that is, unconscious desires and internal conflicts that are beyond the person's control are also at the source of the psychological problems experienced. Psychic traumas, especially experienced between the ages of 0 and 5, are shown as an important factor that forms the basis of conflicts experienced in adulthood.

CURRENT SCIENCE

Basic concept in psychoanalytic psychotherapy: Sometimes, psychosexual developmental stages may not be successfully resolved and integrated in some people. When this process, which we call psychosexual developmental periods, cannot be successfully resolved and integrated, there is a rate of development of some different types of personality disorders in individuals, and it varies from individual to individual. When basic conflicts are not resolved and suppressed, a high degree of anxiety arises in the individual and in the individual's brain, which leads to psychic disorders through unconscious processes. These anxieties may appear as an anxiety disorder in the future.

The main purpose of therapy in psychoanalytic therapy is: By raising the target unconscious, which was originally determined by the mental health doctor in psychoanalytic therapy, to deal with the disturbing experiences more consciously and clearly, by working on the inner conflicts of the individual who has been suppressed, by increasing the mental and at the same time the emotional awareness of the individual. Restructuring the basic personality of the individual emerges as the main and main goal in psychoanalytic psychotherapy.

Therapist-client relationship in therapy within psychoanalytic psychotherapy: The therapist works in the background as a neutral and expert. The therapist, by revealing his knowledge in his inner world, deals with the meaning of the client's behavior and his interest in the past, the way he describes the past and the forms of his behavior, and then makes comments to the client. The client may also develop projections towards the therapist.

Therapy technique in psychoanalytic therapy: In psychoanalytic therapy, especially the analysis of dreams, free association, interpretation, resistance, and transference analysis can be among the basic techniques. And thanks to these techniques (analysis of dreams, free association, interpretation, resistance, and transference analyses), unconscious situations, emotions and thoughts that create traumas to the individual in case of internal conflicts are easily revealed. In this way, while gaining insight, unconscious inner conflicts can be revealed in addition to this, unconscious material is understood by the ego, and efforts are initiated to move forward on the way of solving the problem by making in-depth examinations on the person.

The positive and negative aspects of psychoanalytic psychotherapy on the individual: It is a long and expensive method. However, it is a method where time and value can be spent both in terms of time and money. Social, cultural, and personal factors can be ignored. By ignoring these factors, biological and impulsive factors are given more weight. It does not have a suitable structure in solving small problems in daily life. It is generally used for the treatment of more

CURRENT SCIENCE

serious and long-lasting illness or disease symptoms. Behavior formation, personality structure and functioning of the individual, ego defense mechanisms can break new ground on anxiety. It is very suitable for both individual and group therapy. It is not a study recommended for psychotic individuals.

4- Adlerian Therapy

In the Adlerian psychotherapy method, from the first moment the problems of the past started, the effects of the individual to the present are concerned with the future without underestimating and skipping. It is assumed that the decisions taken by the individuals, namely the clients, are still based on the experiences of the individual in the current time and the individual decides according to the direction in which he/she progresses, and the individual is evaluated in that way. "People live with their dreams" is a very well-known phrase and is still widely used today, and this phrase "Man lives with dreams" is a structure that summarizes Adlerian philosophy in a very clear and beautiful way. The effort to overcome the feeling of inferiority and all the strength, effort and ambition needed to be perfect are considered as an innate ability in all people. The goal of superiority is considered as the most important thing that ensures the development and change of almost all humanity. Individuals can easily cope with negative feelings such as unhappiness and anxiety, while striving for success, superiority, competence, power, power. In Adlerian psychotherapy, therapists see their clients, namely their clients, as artists with great talent and creative abilities. They handle all kinds of feelings and thoughts by thinking that they are perfect people. Our lifestyle is just one of the ways we express our life. We set the goal of establishing superiority, and while advancing and making efforts in this direction, some people develop their intelligence, some people develop their artistic abilities, some people develop their sportive skills, and some people develop their educational features. Everyone in a society is influenced by their unique lifestyles in every way.

In Adlerian psychotherapy, the approach of clients towards themselves, as well as the approach towards other individuals, and new ways of being interested in life and gaining motivation are tried to be shown. In Adlerian psychotherapy, the clients who have consulted a mental health doctor are discouraged and unhappy due to false beliefs, false or false values, and false or undesirable goals that the individual forces himself to be desired, and in addition to these, actions that are full of stress are encouraged and aimed to be restructured. In the approach of Adlerian psychotherapy, the diagnosis of a mental disorder is especially avoided because it is

CURRENT SCIENCE

based on the idea that individuals can overcome the symptoms of mental disorders better and faster by not putting themselves into that psychology. The client is approached within the framework of a more developmental understanding and with as positive a thought as possible. In therapy, individuals are given as much support as possible to help clients understand themselves better and without getting angry and hard on themselves, and to overcome their past traumas and difficulties, in addition to changing their own life stories. In Adlerian psychotherapy, the relationship between the client and the therapist is generally based on mutual belief, respect, trust, love, and a common aim of goals, and there is an equal relationship between the two parties (the psychiatrist, that is, the therapist and the client who has consulted with the mental health doctor). At the beginning of therapy, the main goal is to establish that personal connection between the client and the therapist before the problem. Instead of using techniques or similar mechanical approaches, the client's subjective experiences should be based on and should be proceeded in this way. In Adlerian psychotherapy, ways to make a difference in clients' lives are explored. This difference is provided by changes made on behavior, thought or perception of the individual.

5- Existential Therapy

William Barrett has a famous book on existentialism, and in this famous book William Barret speaks of a pensive man who was so isolated from his own life and didn't even know he existed until he found himself dead one morning, and said, "Each of us has not yet reached the roots of our own existence one day. We can find ourselves in a dead state as a human being."

What is existential psychotherapy? We can also answer this question by considering it as a method that makes a deep inquiry about the structure of human existence and anxiety, sadness, hopelessness, loneliness, isolation and reasonlessness, and purposelessness. The concepts of meaning, creativity, and especially love have largely reserved a place for himself in all these questions. When viewed, there are two basic concepts in existentialism.

There is a condition called non-authentic mode. In the so-called non-authentic mode, the individual lives his/her own life as an anonymous life. To truly be himself, the individual avoids taking any responsibility regardless of what it is and looks to temporarily get rid of situations related to his own self or environmental concerns, that is, to save the day, by surrendering himself to the definitions of the self and the world made with external factors. He moves in line

CURRENT SCIENCE

with approved habits and existing traditions and feels temporarily happy and satisfied, indulging in a false sense of security.

In the authentic mode, even if the person feels any anxiety about his own self or his environment, he takes responsibility for his own life in every process and condition. Even at the cost of abandoning the comfort of being an indistinct, unobtrusive individual in the crowd, he becomes aware of his own uniqueness, does so, and strives to be what he really should be. Behaviors that show themselves as not towards themselves or any other individual. The perception of being himself/herself outweighs those people, and they are placed in a secondary position in society to adapt to the world. The person is aware of the fragility arising from his existence, and in addition, the same individual is aware of the responsibilities brought by his existence.

Almost always, individuals have been caught between these two choices during an adventure that stretches from the very beginning of human history to the present. Depending on the herd psychology, the false sense of security, that is, temporary safety, obtained with the aim of not leaving the society, or the unbearable weight of the self after losing the self, or the energy and enthusiasm created by the state of existence, even if it arouses anxiety in the individual. .

A person with authentic features stays in constant contact with the individual physically and, in addition, spiritually. While the person struggles to put his life in order, he is also conscious of the possibilities, restrictions and finally the obstacles on this path. Existential psychotherapy practice aims and provides these kinds of things, which we can refer to as simplifying or facilitating realism at this point.

In existential therapy, vague complaints about deficiencies in purpose and meaning are at the forefront of referrals to mental health professionals and mental health doctors. Choosing, taking responsibility and being mortal are also included in this spiral. It may be more practical and faster to consider and evaluate the complaints of clients who have consulted mental health specialists, namely mental health doctors, as only certain symptoms and alleviate them. However, this situation should not be evaluated and handled in this way because, no matter how practical and fast, treatments that do not try to find the meaning of life and do not encourage individuals to gain a more positive perspective on life and embark on life will never be able to live beyond being palliative solutions.

CURRENT SCIENCE

Existential psychotherapy has emerged for this, in short, to produce more permanent solutions in response to such problems.

There are certain important concepts in existential therapy, and one of these so-called certain important concepts is the concept of freedom. The concept of "freedom" is a very important concept in existential therapy. The concept of freedom mentioned here is that "individuals become the authors of their own lives, and all people live harmoniously or discordantly in the same universe, regardless of whether it is an eternal design". Life unfoundedly confronts individuals, and everyone is responsible for their own choices. Regardless of whether the situation that arises because of a choice made by an individual is bad or good, the individual should take responsibility for the situation that occurs because of his work. This existentialist concept of freedom carries more responsibility than it seems, and at the same time, the choice made by the individual due to fears of taking responsibility in addition to the fear of failure or failure causes great anxiety on the individual. Due to this and many similar reasons, many people try to escape from this freedom, try all kinds of ways to escape, and then fall into the desire to surrender. However, another important meaning of being in the world, that is, the meaning he gives to the world, is that he feels responsibility for his actions and failures and takes this responsibility. What each individual needs individually to complete the responsibility is the individual's own will.

In the world, especially in recent years, the concept of will is mentioned together with motivation and presented in this way. Individuals have also recently considered this concept of will as an escape route. They can do this both voluntarily and unconsciously. Explaining a behavior of an individual with the help of a certain motivation is an excuse for the individual who does that behavior to avoid all responsibility for his own behavior, and in addition, the person is far from being authentic. Here, certain pathological defense mechanisms come into play and thus, psychological disorders in the individual emerge easily. The existential psychotherapy method does not matter whether it is right or wrong, from the choice one makes, it allows the individual to take responsibility for his own experiences and at the same time, so that the individual will easily find inner peace.

Another concept in existentialism and existential therapy is isolation. The fact that we come into the world alone and return alone is a major cause for anxiety in existentialism. As human beings, we always have a desire to be in contact with others. We must manage the tension between this desire and our consciousness of our loneliness. Erich Fromm counts isolation as

CURRENT SCIENCE

one of the main sources of anxiety. The fact that death always occurs alone is at the core of the feeling of isolation. Also, many people have a frightening feeling that there will be times when no one in the world thinks about them. At the point where the person takes full responsibility for his own life, he also faces the perception of existential isolation.

The situation called making sense of life appears as a completely different concept in existential psychotherapy. Even if nothing is certain and not given to us, everyone must find some different meaning in life. This is important for individuals to continue their lives. Everyone has an obligation to create their own worlds, and everyone must find satisfying and satisfying answers on this and many other issues such as why he lives, how he should live in addition to this, what is right and how he wants to live. One of the most important and at the same time basic tasks in the life of every living person is to find a purpose that is strong enough to carry his life from an empty event to a meaningful point. There are questions like "I don't have ambition for anything, why am I living, just being successful doesn't satisfy me, I'm at this age, but I still don't know what I want to do for a reason I don't even know why, I want to live life more deeply" and this is what has just been counted. Questions put the individual into a mental depression. Even if the duration of these thoughts to depress individuals varies, if the person does not know himself, if he does not know himself, this period will last for a very short time and eventually he will experience that period of depression. For this reason, things such as helping the individual find his or her main purpose or goals in life are among the main tasks of psychotherapy applied by therapists. This is based on existential psychotherapy.

The last and most difficult question in existentialism and defined as the last and most difficult question in existentialism is the state of our awareness of our mortality. This situation can sometimes cause a lot of anxiety in individuals with certain thought systems and cause anxiety disorders. At the same time, this situation can sometimes be called the most painful situation in psychology. Whatever individuals do, their existence will eventually come to an end, and this is called the inevitable end of everyone. There is an important thing that individuals need to know, which can create a very good thought system for their psychology, sometimes it is possible in daily life to see a storm approaching from afar even in the sunniest, calmest moment. Just because it's sunny, there's no such thing as a storm or a rain. Individuals should live in the shadow of this awareness to have a healthier psychology. Of course, every minute that individuals have in their life should not be spent in fear of death. Because if individuals spend every minute of their lives with this fear and anxiety, the anxiety caused by the fear of death, it will create great anxiety in the individual.

CURRENT SCIENCE

Individuals develop some compulsive behaviors to soften the fear and anxiety that death brings, including having an unshakable belief that someone will eventually come to their rescue and work hard for that individual more than anything else, dedicating himself to trying to be rich and famous, and projecting himself into the future through his children. Methods are often used to overcome this state of fear and anxiety. Having an intense anxiety about non-existence also makes future possibilities impossible. Fears of death or death traumas may lie behind many mental disorders. Accepting to face death is a very important step and being ready for it will help the individual to live more fulfilling, rich and at the same time more compassionate lives. If we see death as a source that enriches a life, this situation will reduce the anxiety in individuals, and a peaceful, happier, stress-free life will be opened. Existential psychotherapy continues to work on these goals.

In existential psychotherapy, the individual is seen clinically as any being in pain, not as a person in a difficult situation governed by the individual's past, present situation, confused mind, or impulses that constantly disturb the individual. Almost all the problems of individuals start from the first moment they are born and increase when the individual develops and begins to realize something.

From this point of view, existential psychotherapy, which is considered separately from many psychotherapy methods, focuses directly on life itself, instead of looking for the source of conflict in the past events itself or in the distorted thoughts of the individual. When a life is examined, that life will confront the individual with almost everything from the very beginning to the present, along with his own existence, and in addition, it will lead to remarkable positive reactions, among other things. Feelings of purposelessness in life, boredom, generalized anxiety and dissatisfaction in the individual, which have led many individuals to psychotherapy, support the existential basis of psychological conflicts. Therefore, depending on this, existential psychotherapy often takes place among important treatments, both independently and in other psychotherapy methods. To summarize, "What is existential psychotherapy? We can answer the question "" as a therapy method that aims to restore the loss of happiness that occurs with the loss of emotional pleasure and tastes.

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CURRENT SCIENCE

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